

DEVELOPING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN'S PHYSICAL ATTRIBUTES USING INTERACTIVE GAMES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the use of movement games as a means of physical qualities through the use of movement games in physical children, and on this basis to identify the theoretical foundations and methods of technology development of children's movement activities in preschool institutions. It is planned to conduct research on the organization of physical education and public health activities for the development of children's physical activity in the context of preschool education.*

Keywords: *preschool education, movement play, movement activity, physical education, physical development, physical qualities, fitness, ability, physiological factors, muscle, vegetative organ activity.*

At the meeting chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyayev on August 16, 2017, the important tasks were drifted on radically reforming the system of preschool education, the full coverage of children in these institutions. As a result of the analysis, in a short period of time, three major documents, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, PD-3261 "On measures to radically improve the system of preschool education." Decree No. PF-5198 of September 30 "On measures to radically improve the management of the preschool education system" and PO "On the organization of the activities of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" - Resolution 3305 were adopted.

The purpose of the above-mentioned decrees and orders is to create the conditions for the next generation to grow up healthy. A healthy generation means a healthy country, and the task of educating a healthy generation is primarily the responsibility of preschool institutions.

The humanization of preschool education is the basis of the process of its renewal. Scientists and practitioners are increasingly concluding that the physical education system for preschool children should have a comprehensive, human impact on the individual, ensuring that every child's right to regular and full physical development to be realized. The environment around children is changing. Simple games have been replaced by computer games. Mental and aesthetic development of the child is a priority. Without denying their importance, it should be noted that the child's time for active games, walks, communication with peers is decreasing.

Other types of play and child activities, such as imbalances between different types of play (interactive and sitting, separate and joint), have a negative impact on both the health of preschool children and the level of development of movement skills.

The search for new ways to solve the problems of physical development of preschool children is associated, firstly, with the need to resolve these contradictions, and secondly, with the need to study the laws, methodological and methodological conditions for improving the physical fitness of the younger generation.

A serious feature of early infancy is the interdependence and interdependence of the child's health, physical development.

Accordingly, it is important to find and justify effective ways to increase the physical fitness of preschool children, to develop their movement skills, to increase their interest in movement based on vital needs such as agility, strength, courage.

It is not exaggeration to say that the solution to this problem lies in the creation of a holistic educational process, a unity of socio-pedagogical conditions that ensure the balanced physical and personal development of the child in all respects,

In this case, the games are most valuable forms of organizing of children's movement activities.

However, the issue of targeted development of physical qualities and mental processes of preschool children on the basis of action games has not been discussed in detail in some studies.

Therefore, the purpose of working on this topic is to identify the theoretical foundations and methodological approaches to the development of children's movement skills in preschool education through the use of movement games as a means of physical education.

In the process of achieving this goal, research on the organization of physical education and public health activities for the development of children's physical activity in preschool institutions will help to solve the above problem.

The subject of the work is to update the content, form, means and methods of the theoretical basis for the development of technology for the development of children's physical activity in the context of preschool education.

In the application of this subject, it is advisable to make the following assumption, including the views about the theoretical substantiation of the process of development of children's movement activity in the context of preschool education.

Implementing this direction in children's physical education can also significantly improve the impact of the use of traditional tools, particularly movement games, to develop children's movement skills.

The age characteristics of improving the physical fitness of preschool children have been identified, their development in the context of preschool education is justified theoretically and experimentally, for which the followings have been identified:

1. Age features of the development of physical qualities processes based on the use of movement games in the physical education of preschool children;
2. The laws of the relationship between the basic physical qualities of preschool children;
3. Means and methods of influencing the physical qualities and development of preschool children.

The practical and theoretical significance of the work is that the scientific data obtained in the course of the research to clarify the laws of the theory and methods of physical education related to the problems of improving the educational process in the context of preschool education. Technology for the development of children's movement activity in the context of preschool education will be developed and theoretically substantiated.

Features of the development of physical qualities in preschool children are mainly the fact that as soon as a child is born, his blood is endowed with an appropriate set of physical abilities placed by individual genetic programs of development.

During the biological maturation of body structures the organs develop individual capabilities and determine various physical characteristics of a person. According to EA Pimonova, LV Karmanova, and others, the overall positive trends in children's physical development over the

past 20 years (an increase in all body sizes) have seen a slight increase in their movement, and a number of indicators (speed, speed-power capabilities) are significantly reduced. Nevertheless, experts believe that the training of physical qualities should begin exactly in the preschool period.

Physiological factors in the development of qualitative aspects of motor activity in children and adolescents are reflected in the improvement of the management of muscle and autonomic organs. In short-term, agility and strength movements, more emphasis is placed on improving the management of the nervous system.

In some long-term activities, along with the improvement of motor functions, the coordination of autonomic functions is also important.

However, the most important role in improving the physiological control of the functions of children and adolescents, which determine the improvement of strength, speed and endurance, is the formation of connections that improve the functions of the nervous system, especially muscle tension.

Thus, the physiological mechanisms that determine the various forms of interdependence of strength, speed, and endurance in childhood are also diverse.

Conditioned-reflex factors are important.

During exercise, certain forms of programming the muscles and autonomic organs in the central nervous system occur for movements that develop strength, speed, or endurance in a particular direction. Interactive games maximize the implementation of the task of complex development of movement skills, because their content is focused on shaping and replacing action programs.

It is well known that the experience of movement that a person acquires in the process of development is reflected in the emergence and strengthening of different levels of movement programs. The more diverse the movement skills, the more opportunities there are to learn new movements.

Interactive games are characterized by the frequent alternation of states, movements, and movement activities of the body and its parts, which are complex systems. In pedagogical practice, the subjects are differentiated with action and didactic games.

Interactive games are very important in children's physical education, action games can have small, medium, and large levels of mobility. Preschoolers learn natural movements through games (walking, running, jumping, throwing, crawling) Interactive games are one of the main means of physical education of children.

They can be allowed from the age of two. During this time, children begin to develop life skills such as running, jumping, throwing, and climbing. Older preschoolers will be able to assess their movements and abilities as they compete in strength (pulling in the arms), speed (running short distances, jogging) and other qualities. In addition to physical development, movement games help children develop qualities such as willpower, courage, perseverance, endurance, and courage. Children usually try to meet their huge needs for movement through games. For them, game and activity is in the first place.

During movement games, children's movements improve the qualities such as initiative and independence, confidence and determination develop.

They learn to coordinate their actions, and even to follow certain rules (initially, of course, in a simple way). Children under the age of three are usually very impressionable, einteractiveal,

unstable, they are active, but they get tired quickly from a variety of movements, and cannot walk (run) for long periods without a break.

Therefore, it is necessary to control very active children: not to let them hang in their arms, not to jump from great heights, to draw their attention to slower games.

Gradually, the content of the games will change. Children first follow the instructions of adults: for example, they describe a chicken or a bird - "they grind grain", "they fly".

At the age of three, children move from imitating the actions of adults to various "pictorial" or role-playing games. They play role-playing or figurative games, portraying a doctor, a salesman, a driver, a cook, and more. Children actively repeat not only familiar actions, but also what they see.

The longer the game lasts, the more diverse and clear the plot becomes. Later, the game becomes more complicated. There are three roles, for example, one child depicts a sheep, another a wolf, and a third a shepherd. Independent action games with a variety of toys are very useful. Children can be grouped into two or three. A child's movements are usually determined by the type of toy, for example, running with flags, hoops, driving cars, rolling balls, throwing, hanging.

Children are interested in such toys. In any independent game, children may not immediately show activity and initiative, their movements are identical and limited. But in adult-related games, children's actions are goal-oriented, they repeat movements over and over again, strengthening movement skills, developing agility, dexterity. It is important for children to be guided, even when they are playing. It is advisable to complicate the game of some of them, to teach others to finish what they started, and to talk if the third is playing quietly. Often in independent play, children make wrong and even dangerous actions. They jump over a chair or pole with their feet almost straight, leaning on the soles of their feet; they are pushed off the ground with the soles of their feet. There are several ways to do this. The adult enters the game himself, reminding the children of a familiar and close image they can imitate (how soft a cat jumps, how birds fly silently).

The first games that need to be taught to children do not have a specific plot and rules. The child completes simple, fun tasks, comes and picks up the toy, runs to the adults and sees what is hidden in their hands. Examples include "Get the Flag," "Run to me," and "Find the Flag." There is a certain consistency in teaching games. For example, "Catch Me" is simpler than "Catch Me". In the first case, the child has to hold an adult, in the second game there is a risk of being caught, so the child has to use more physical force.

The games need to be more diverse in content and include more complex tasks. If the child initially ran as fast as he or she wanted to get the toy, the speed of the run should be determined by the adult after the game has been well mastered.

In the course of the research, we focused on the following tasks;

1. To study the age-related features of the development of children's physical activity in the context of preschool education, as well as to identify specific features of the interdependence of indicators of physical fitness of children.

2. Determine and theoretically substantiate the development of children's motor activity in the context of preschool education through experiments and the technology of development of children's motor activity.

The planning of experiments on physical education of preschool children was carried out on the basis of the scheme presented in Table 1. For five weeks, preschoolers consistently

performed specially graded movement games for this purpose, which were matched to one or more of the five physical qualities as they developed more strongly with one or more of the mental process indicators.

For example, power and attention, power and imagination. In addition to strength capabilities, growths in agility, agility, endurance, and flexibility in relation to mental processes, age, and gender were also studied. Over the course of five weeks, the children performed at least 12 movement games aimed at developing one of the five different mental qualities more strongly.

Table 1

Expert assessments of interactive games for stronger development of physical qualities (5 points) Preschool children (3-4 years)

№	Game Name	Physical Attributes				
		Strength	Aptness	Agility	Flexibility	Endurance
1	Jump to the line	2		3		
2	Who shoots away	5				
3	Walk over the hills	2		3		
4	Shoot the ball	3	2			
5	Jump on the stick	3		2		
6	Pass the ball to your partner	2	1	2		
7	Jump down and dream	3		2		
8	Chickens in the garden		1	2	2	
9	A white rabbit is sitting	2		3		
10	Longer horse	3		2		
11	Horse on a rope	3		2		
12	Sniper	2,5		2,5		
13	Sparrows	2	1	2		
14	Get the ball	2,5		2,5		
15	One foot down the road	2	1	1		1
16	From ring to ring	2,5		2,5		

As a result of statistical processing, 14 tests were selected for each of the four age groups of girls and boys to assess their physical fitness in accordance with the requirements of the test theory of performance control exercises by children aged 3-6 years. The content of the tests in each age-sex group had its own characteristics. For example, the following tests were used to characterize the endurance of 3-year-old girls: running 60 and 120 m; Running 70 and 120 m for 4 year olds; 90 and 120 m running for 5 year olds; For 6-year-olds, Running to the first stop and 120m run. This means that only one test was repeated for all age groups - running 120 m. Details on how to use this or that test are given below. Here are the data of pedagogical experiment conducted at the pre-school educational establishment No. 25 in Urgench city.

The experiment and control group consisted of peer children, using 61 training lessons and 244 different action games in the experiment. The planning of the pedagogical experiment was carried out as follows. Prior to the start of the experiment, all children underwent a follow-up test to determine the initial state of development of physical qualities and mental processes. Then, over a 25-day study period, the children in the experimental group performed stratified movement

games to further develop one of the five physical attribute according to the scheme shown in Table 2. At the end of the 25-day probationary period, the children again switched to control exercises, the purpose of which was to evaluate the results of the pedagogical experiment relative to the initial indicators. The next physical attribute was studied in the same manner over the next 25 days. Thus, a total of 5 different physical attribute checks were performed over 75 training days.

Table 2

**Expert assessments on the stronger development of physical qualities of interactive games
 (5 points) Preschool children (5-6 years)**

№	Game Name	Physical Attributes				
		Strength	Aptness	Agility	Flexibility	Endurance
1	Who runs farther	2				3
2	Jump on the pole					5
3	The rope forward					5
4	We are football players					5
5	Roundelay		2			3
6	Make no mistake		5			
7	Invisible		2	3		
8	Slow running		2			3
9	The lesson is on the stairs					5
10	From the stairs					5
11	Running over obstacles					5
12	To the gate				5	
13	Vibrating bumps				5	
14	The legs are behind the head				5	
15	Move your hand				5	
16	Put it in place				5	
17	Go under the stick				5	
18	Go over the stick				5	
19	Go through the ring				5	

There were no significant differences in the initial status of children aged 3–6 years in the control and experimental group. Therefore, in the subsequent analysis of the results of the pedagogical experiment, we only compare the final results.

Examining the Possibilities of Strength in the Development of Physical Qualities in Children during the Experimental Period (Three-year-olds).

Preliminary studies conducted prior to the experiment showed significant differences in the development of the right and left hand palm in three-year-old boys. The differences showed that the superiority of the right hand was reliable ($t_{q3}, 29$). At the same time, there was no significant difference between the forces on the girls' right and left palms. A final study 25 days later found that both boys and girls had increased strength in their right and left hand palms and wrists.

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